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Abstract: The article examines the features of the postmodern image of the family as a social institution, the lives of the heroes, and their worldview. Having analyzed the cultural level of characters in family relationships, their understanding of such values as family and love, the author comes to the conclusion that L. Petrushevskaya was trying to describe the crisis of the family. The characters, forced to be in the same space, are separated and lonely; each of them perceives love differently.

Key words: literature, family, love, life of heroes, family values, originality of the author's work.

Petrushevskaya's work, as noted by all critics without exception, is implicated in dark collisions that are "not philosophically existential, but of a reduced everyday nature" [1]. Her characters are locked in the elements of kitchen and communal squabbles.

From the very beginning of Petrushevskaya's creative activity, the shadow sides of reality were in the center of her attention. However, the mere saturation of texts with negative life material, which did not go beyond the everyday sphere, could not in the sixties cause a complete ban on publication. As is known, it was during this period that a number of works devoted to the so-called prison camp theme appeared in print - this important page in the history of Russian literature was opened by A. Solzhenitsyn's famous story "One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich" (1962). A sharp and mercilessly truthful portrayal of the negative aspects of Soviet life was also characteristic of the so-called village prose. Its founder, according to most researchers, was the same Solzhenitsyn, who published the story "Matrenin's Dvor" (1963) on the pages of Novy Mir.

Indeed, at first glance, the works of the "village dwellers" depict an even more dirty and unsettled life than in Petrushevskaya's prose and drama. Pictures of spiritual and moral degradation and even savagery of a significant part of society, presented, for example, in the aforementioned "Matryona's Yard" or in V. Belov's story "A Habitual Business," are capable of striking any imagination. The authors of these works, with all their might, cannot be blamed for trying to embellish at least something in the empirical reality of Soviet life at that time and

somehow smooth out its contradictions. For example, residents of the village of Talnovo, where the action of Solzhenitsyn's story takes place, are forced to work virtually for free on collective farm fields, they are deprived of the opportunity to legally obtain fuel to heat their houses and are faced with the need to steal peat; In the local store, only barley groats and combined fat are freely sold, and "margarine is in great demand." The main character, the elderly peasant woman Matryona, is, among other things, deprived of even the insignificant pension that she is entitled to, and as a result, the entire household of the hardworking collective farmer consists of a ficus tree, a cat and a goat. All of Matryona's fellow villagers are portrayed as pathologically greedy and envious people who are indifferent to spiritual and moral values.

In her dramatic works, the writer tried to depict the shadow sides of life. Her characters experience physical pain and mental trauma. According to N. Leiderman and M. Lipovetsky, Lyudmila Stefanovna depicts the crisis of the family as a social institution: "Petrushevskaya's dramatic situation always reveals the distortion of human relationships, especially in the family or between a man and a woman; the abnormality and pathology of these relationships invariably leads her characters to despair and a feeling of insurmountable loneliness" [2. P. 113].

The love depicted by the author takes different forms, and this feeling does not always become the basis for family relationships. Thus, in the story "Time is Night" (1988 – 1990), published in the magazine "New World" in 1992, the heroine's love for her grandson makes everyone around her and even the child unhappy. Anna Andrianovna asserts herself through self-denial in love. The heroine is fiercely fighting to create a comfortable life and is busy looking for a means of livelihood. In order to feed her grandson, left in her care by her daughter Alena, she herself refuses to eat, divides the bread for a week, and on the hungriest days she goes to visit friends who are already tired of periodically feeding them ("I behave like the Queen of England, I refuse everything, what from everything: tea with crackers and sugar! I drink their tea only with my brought bread, I nip it out of the bag involuntarily, because the pangs of hunger at someone else's table are unbearable, Tima leaned on the crackers and asked if it was possible with butter (the butter dish was forgotten on the table). "What about you?" asks Masha, but it's important for me to feed Timofey: no, thank you, spread it thicker for Timochka, do you want Tim, more? And I quickly grabbed a few more crackers, good cream crackers, I'm taking Tim out of the kitchen to watch TV. Oh, what are you, bread... Thank you. No, we won't have another, I see you're tired, from work. Well, maybe just Timofeika. Tim, will you have some meat? Only for him, only for him (unexpectedly I'm crying, this is my weakness)" [6. Vol. 1]). At the same time, the heroine, sitting at someone else's table as a guest, understands that they are not welcome, that people are forced to feed them, since Timofeyka unceremoniously asks for food,

and if the owners say some harsh phrases, then the child's face is distorted with a nervous tic ("Everything ", there is no more way for us to come here, I kept this house as a large reserve, for a completely last resort. That's it, now, as a last resort, we will have to look for other channels" [6, Vol. 1]).

A specific feature of Petrushevskaya's dramaturgy is the very widely represented techniques from the arsenal of the theater of the absurd. Moreover, the shift into a deliberate convention performs various functions in the writer's plays, now revealing the tragic and infernal hidden behind the everyday bustle, now revealing the comic absurdity of what is happening, now explicating the motive of longing for a transcendental ideal.

Petrushevskaya in her work - both in prose and in drama - in an original way synthesizes the features inherent in the so-called canonically traditional realism with the features of postmodern play poetics. It seems that the most successful term to denote the specifics of its discourse is "post-realism".

In general, Petrushevskaya's artistic system is an invariant model open to dialogue: it combines incompatible things, while everything exists simultaneously. Thus, the heroes of the works discussed above, although they are relatives, nevertheless inflict psychological and physical trauma on each other and try to get rid of their children as if they were a heavy burden. Petrushevskaya's naturalistic depiction of the life of the heroes in the works "Love" and "Time is Night" symbolizes the crisis of the family as a social institution. The characters have long been in pseudo-family relationships, but stubbornly call themselves a family in the traditional sense.

Today, many critics consider the most pressing task for modern Russian literature to be "overcoming" postmodernism, of course, not in the sense of its primitive denial, but in terms of the intelligent use of all its most fruitful achievements. It seems that Lyudmila Petrushevskaya has advanced further towards this goal than others. That is why her work deserves the closest attention and in-depth study.

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